

Tissue Classification Using RNA Splice Junctions with Distribution Analysis and Machine Learning Models*

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Abstract—The human body generates more proteins than it has genes that code for proteins. The diversity of proteins stems from the alternative ways in which RNA can be spliced and reassembled. Each alternative version of RNA produces a different protein, providing a way for our bodies to produce a wide range of proteins with a single gene. Some alternative RNA transcripts, however, have splicing errors and produce faulty proteins involved in genetic diseases. Understanding splicing patterns and profiles has wide implications for our understanding of healthy and diseased tissue states. Currently little is known regarding the splicing profiles of healthy tissue which vary across individuals and within individuals by tissue type. Therefore, this project explored the use of RNA splicing data from the first chromosome to predict the tissue type of non-cancerous samples using distribution analysis and supervised learning methods. The Kolmogorov-Smirnov test was used to classify the samples based on empirical cumulative distribution functions and was not able to reliably distinguish between tissue types. However using Support Vector Models (SVM) we had high classification accuracy, even when using different splice junction representations. Overall, the findings suggest the utility of using splice junction data in biological classification and sets the foundation for future work of mapping splicing patterns with phenotype

Index Terms—RNA-seq, Tissue Classification, Splice junctions, Distribution analysis, Support vector machines

I. INTRODUCTION

According to the central dogma of molecular biology proposed by Francis Crick in 1970 [1], genetic information stored as DNA is transcribed to RNA prior to translation into proteins, which were mainly considered to be the functional drivers of biology at the time. While today we continue to uncover novel biological functions of RNA beyond coding proteins, we have come to appreciate the significance of evaluating total RNA content, or the “transcriptome,” as providing one of the most accessible and comprehensive snapshots of a sample’s epigenetic status.

The amount and variety of RNA that is expressed differ by cell and tissue types (e.g. liver vs. whole blood) and using RNA sequencing (RNA-seq) we can quantify the RNA

expression levels for different tissue samples [2]. Alternative transcripts are products of different splicing patterns from a single gene, and each transcript can produce a different protein variant or isoform. For example, the Human BCL-2 gene is a regulator of apoptosis; however, there are isoforms of BCL-2 that are pro-apoptotic and isoforms that are anti-apoptotic [3]. These isoforms share much of the same sequence, so only RNA sequencing reads that directly cover the unique regions differentiating these isoforms from one another are useful for interpreting the apoptotic status based on BCL-2 expression. For these reasons our aim was to utilize RNA splice junction as the features or predictors of meaningful biological classification. Splice junctions indicate the location coordinates of where the RNA splicing occurred or the location coordinates of the intron boundaries. The coordinates are composed of a ‘donor’ and ‘acceptor’ identifier within the genomic sequence. Splice junctions can capture fuller information about gene expression levels and functionality, and so we aimed to evaluate the utility of splicing coordinates in predicting tissue type in healthy samples as a foundational step for deriving splice junction profiles in healthy physiology. To achieve this we developed several different feature engineering methods using a combination of different filtering techniques and representations of RNA splicing data.

II. METHODOLOGY

A. Data

Our RNA sequencing data came from the Genotype-Tissue Expression (GTEx) dataset. The GTEx dataset consists of 54 different types of tissues from the autopsies of 548 unique donors. We generated a fastq file containing fragments of nucleotide sequences from every detectable RNA molecule in a sample. These sequences were then aligned to the sample’s appropriate genome and compared to gene annotations curated over the last few decades in order to produce an alignment file that maps each sequencing read to a gene or genomic locus [4].

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Fig. 1. 'Muscle - Skeletal' population empirical pdf.

B. Feature Engineering

The following sections describe the data processing, splice junction representations and proposed models of two different splice junction representations. For both methods we extracted splice junctions only from Chromosome 1 as opposed to the whole genome. Limiting our analysis to Chromosome 1, which is the second largest chromosome and makes up a sizable proportion of the splicing events, helped to reduce computation burden while still allowing us to examine the usefulness of splicing junction data.

1) *Distributional Representation*: For this set of features, we choose to include the two tissue types from the GTEx dataset which contain the most tissue samples ('Muscle - Skeletal' and 'Whole Blood') in addition to three tissue types from the brain: 'Brain - Spinal cord (cervical c-1),' 'Brain - Caudate (basal ganglia),' and 'Brain - Nucleus accumbens (basal ganglia)'. The three brain tissues were added to increase the difficulty of the tissue classification task. Using these five classes we had a sample size of 1080, with heavy class imbalance. Both 'Muscle - Skeletal' and 'Whole Blood' contain approximately 400 tissue samples after the preliminary data cleaning phase, although all tissues included from the brain contained fewer than 100 tissue samples.

As seen in Figure 1, the distribution of splice junction sites observed in a sample are accounted for by the few most frequently occurring junction sites. Because of this, we decided to include the top-500 most frequently occurring splice junction sites to reduce dimensionality. We normalized the quantification data on the tissue sample level after the top-500 had been selected. We designated this feature set as the 'Distribution Representation,' because we subsequently understand the normalized top-500 most frequent splice junctions in a tissue sample to represent the distribution of splice junctions for that sample.

For this subset, the distribution of the donor and acceptor sites for a given tissue class are almost identical. Therefore we proceeded with our distribution analysis considering only the distribution of donor locations as a proxy for the splice junction location. In practice, the top-500 most frequently occurring splice junction sites have at most five splice junction sites within the top-500 which are associated with the same donor. Because only a small percentage of splice junction sites are affected by this proxy, we consider it an efficient method

and continued with our analysis.

To conduct a distribution analysis to test our ability to classify a tissue sample as a draw from the tissue class's true population we created a population distribution for each tissue class based on its constituent tissue samples. To do so, we aggregated the number of splice junctions which occurred at each donor site across equivalent donor sites from all samples within a tissue class.

To conduct the Kolmogorov-Smirnov and Wasserstein distance tests we required a sample from the two distributions in question. We accomplished this by drawing samples of donor sites from the population/sample which were directly proportional to those found in the population/sample of interest. We then took the top-100 most frequent splice junction donors from the population of each tissue class. We combined all the top-100 population vectors to allow for overlap of observed tissue sample quantification of a top-500 donor location from a different tissue class than the observation without requiring this to exist. We termed this set of donor locations that are present in at least one top-100 subset drawn from one of the tissue classes as the "donor variables". We then compared this set of donor variables to every tissue sample to achieve a set of vectors containing the proportion of splice junctions observed in the top-500 for each of the donor variables within the tissue sample. The dataset is thereby constructed such that each row represents an observed tissue sample and each column, a donor location. Each value of this table indicates the proportion of the splice junction sites associated with a specific donor location (column) out of all splice junction sites associated with a top-500 splice junction for this tissue sample (row). This feature set is labeled as the 'quantification' feature set throughout the paper.

To compare this feature selection method to one that considered the presence of a splice junction not the normalized quantity of its presence we also developed a 'presence' feature set. The presence feature set simply binarizes the quantification feature set: for every value in the quantification feature set that is not zero, that corresponding value in the presence feature set will be one.

2) *Frequency Representation*: The frequency representation method builds on the distribution representation method by analyzing the top-100 most frequent splice junctions, and these splice junctions were drawn from a concatenation of all the unique splice junctions expressed across all tissue samples. To increase the sample size, nine tissues from the GTEx dataset with the highest sample counts were selected, resulting in a total sample size of 3,280 (Table I). Before feature selection the quantification values were normalized within each sample to account for differences in RNA isolation and sequencing, allowing for more accurate comparisons of splice junction quantification across samples. The normalized quantification values were used as feature values, and if a top-100 splice junction was not present in a given sample, then that splice junction feature was assigned a value of zero.

3) *Intersection Representation*: A third feature set was also generated using the intersection of the splice junctions across

TABLE I
NUMBER OF SAMPLES BY TISSUE TYPE USED IN FREQUENCY
REPRESENTATION ANALYSIS

Tissue Type	n
Adipose - Subcutaneous	364
Artery - Tibial	351
Esophagus - Mucosa	326
Lung	331
Muscle - Skeletal	447
Nerve - Tibial	331
Skin - Sun Exposed (Lower leg)	377
Thyroid	337
Whole Blood	416

the tissue samples, which resulted in 11 splice junctions. This method was inspired from previous research that examined the alternative transcripts that were shared across all samples, resulting in quantification values for all splice junctions [5]. However, the SVM accuracy results for this feature set were poor, especially for the classification of adipose, lung and nerve tissues (Average accuracy score: 24.65%, Average balanced accuracy score: 22.11%, Average F1 score: 12.27%). As a result, we will not be focusing on this feature set in this paper.

C. Calculation of Distribution Descriptives

We first conducted a preliminary analysis to derive descriptive statistics of each tissue class based on the tissue samples therein. These descriptive statistics include a naïve measure of the expected value and standard deviation of each tissue class's distribution of donor sites, and a novel method of calculating intraclass deviation. For calculation of the naïve expected value of these distributions we used equation 1.

$$\bar{x} = \sum_{i=1}^n x_i p(x_i) \quad (1)$$

Where x_i is the location of a given donor site i and $p()$ is the proportion of the population's unique splice junction donor sites accounted for by location i . Similarly, for the calculation of the naïve standard deviation of these distributions we used equation 2.

$$\bar{s}^2 = \frac{1}{n-1} \sum_{i=1}^n [x_i - \bar{x}]^2 \quad (2)$$

In equation 2 the variable x_i retains its interpretation, \bar{x} is the expected value of the tissue class, and n is the number of samples observed in the class. When defining our measurement of deviation we chose to focus on the relative presence of splice junction donors between the population of a tissue class and each sample therein. Thus, we use equation 3 to derive a deviation statistic for each tissue class.

$$\sum_{i=1}^p \left| \frac{c_{z_i}}{\sum_{j=1}^m c_{y_j}} - \frac{c_{z_i}}{\sum_{k=1}^n c_{x_k}} \right| \quad (3)$$

In this equation, x_k and y_j represent a donor location observed in the sample and population of a tissue class respectively, where the sample has n elements and the population contains m elements. The set Z , containing z_i with p elements, is the intersection between the donor locations contained in the sample and population. The variable c_{a_b} indicates the count of splice junctions observed in association with donor location a_b . This measurement compares each of the samples to the population by finding the difference between the percentage of splice junction locations found at a given donor site in the sample and population. From this we view a measurement of similarity between each of the samples and the population in terms of the proportional differences between observed splice junction sites. In the ideal situation, each sample of the population will contain the same set of donor locations, and these donor locations will be present in the same proportion across all samples. The deviation metric of this ideal population will be zero.

D. Distribution Representation Classifier Using Distance Tests

For this analysis we utilized two hypothesis tests to investigate the classification power of distribution-based approaches within the confines of our problem. We chose to utilize the Kolmogorov-Smirnov and Wasserstein distance tests to compare the empirical cumulative distribution functions (ECDFs) of our samples. The Kolmogorov-Smirnov test works by calculating a cumulative distribution function (CDF) from the difference of two input ECDFs, and then taking the maximum absolute value of this resulting function as the test statistic [6]. This test statistic is given in equation 4.

$$KS = \max_{x \in \mathbb{R}} |\hat{F}(x) - \hat{E}(x)| \quad (4)$$

The Wasserstein distance test works in a similar way, although it compares the difference between two ECDFs by integrating between both ECDFs to find the area between them and using this area as the test statistic. The formula for the Wasserstein distance statistic is given in equation 5.

$$Wass = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} |\hat{F}(x) - \hat{E}(x)| dx \quad (5)$$

Both tests take as inputs two ECDF functions. In practice the inputs to these functions are two vectors. Each of these vectors represents a sample (draw) of the function, where the aim of the test is to determine if the samples were drawn from the same distribution. To gauge the effectiveness of each of these methods in tissue classification we developed an evaluation statistic to measure the effectiveness of each test in classifying true positives across all samples within a tissue class. We derived a draw from the population of each tissue class and used both the Kolmogorov-Smirnov and Wasserstein distance methods to test if this population sample was drawn from the same distribution as each tissue sample of this class. Using a p-value of 0.05, we recorded whether the result of each of these tests correctly failed to reject the null hypothesis or incorrectly

rejected the null hypothesis (that the two samples were drawn from the same distribution). Finally, we aggregated the number of correct results of each test and divided by the total number of tests conducted to find the proportion of the samples for which the null hypothesis was correctly not rejected.

E. Distribution Representation Classifier Using Support Vector Machines

The SVM approach defines a linear boundary in a transformed version of the high dimensional input space [7] to make classification decisions. SVM is a generalization and extension of methods used to create an optimal separating hyperplane that separates distinct classes to cases where the classes may not be fully separable. SVM uses the data nearest to the class differences to determine the separation boundary, giving the method advantageous properties over methods like linear discriminant analysis (LDA) which use centroids of the classes for this purpose. SVM uses data nearest to class differences by tuning the proportional number of predictions which fall on the wrong side of the separation hyperplane [7].

We conducted two experiments using SVM to classify tissue samples based on transcriptome data. In the first we utilized the quantification data and in the second we utilized the presence data. In both experiments we used the sci-kit learn function for fitting our model and making predictions, and we left the default parameters alone; keeping the penalty term (C) equal to one and the kernel set to a radial kernel ('rbf'). This SVM approach does not use cross validation.

F. Distribution Representation Visualization Using t-distributed Stochastic Neighbor Embedding

To reduce the complexity of the high-dimensional data, t-distributed Stochastic Neighbor Embedding (t-SNE) was applied to visualize the splice junction profiles across tissue types for both quantification and presence data. t-SNE uses a nonlinear dimensionality-reduction method [8] to produce a 2-dimensional visualization of samples that are mapped more closely together if there's greater pairwise similarity while dissimilar samples are placed farther apart from one another. To generate the lower-dimensional points t-SNE minimizes the Kulback-Leibler (KL) divergence between the joint probability of pairwise similarities of data in the high-dimensional space—with similarity being measured using Euclidean distance—and the joint probability of pairwise similarities of low-dimensional points, evaluated using a normalized Student's t-distribution with one degree of freedom.

G. Frequency Representation Classifier Using Support Vector Machine

We trained our SVM model using a radial basis function kernel, a 'one versus one' decision function, and a grid search to tune the hyperparameters, with balanced accuracy selected as the evaluation metric. We used five-fold StratifiedGroupKFold cross-validation to evaluate the model's performance, which was applied to standardized feature values and encoded target values. Our cross-validation method took into

account differences in class sizes and non-independence of 545 samples in our dataset that came from the same donor. We also computed the permutation feature importance for five repetitions to investigate the ranking of splice junction feature importance in improving accuracy. This procedure was run 100 times with different random state values and the average performance metrics are reported in the paper.

H. Frequency Representation Classifier Using Deep Learning

We also experimented with a Multilayer Perceptron (MLP) neural network that contained three hidden layers that were each followed by a ReLU activation function. To improve generalizability, we included batch normalization and dropout layers, with a dropout rate of 0.2. We used the Adam optimizer with a learning rate of .001 and CrossEntropyLoss as the loss function. Our MLP accuracy scores were comparable to those of our SVM models, and we chose to report on the SVM results given their relative simplicity and ability to generate feature importance.

III. RESULTS

A. Distribution Descriptives Results

The results of our preliminary analyses that examined the descriptive statistics of the distribution representation feature set can be viewed in Table II. The figures for naïve expected value and standard deviation refer to the distributions of donor sites in the populations of each tissue class, whereas the figures for deviance utilize the relative proportions of donor locations between each sample and the population of a given tissue class.

We can see from these descriptive statistics that tissues from similar regions share characteristics of their distributions of donor sites. Each of the brain tissue classes has a similar naïve standard deviation, which are approximately an order of magnitude smaller than those of "Muscle - Skeletal" and "Whole Blood". We can see the similarity of tissue also in the two closest tissue classes—"Brain - Caudate (basal ganglia)" and "Brain - Nucleus accumbens (basal ganglia)"—which share a similar naïve standard deviation and expected value of their distributions of donor locations. We can see the deviance metric vary widely between tissue classes, and the interesting observation that the two closest tissue classes—"Brain - Caudate (basal ganglia)" and "Brain - Nucleus accumbens (basal ganglia)"—have the same value for deviance.

B. Results from Distribution Representation Classifier Using Distance Tests

The results of the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test can be seen in Table II. The results of the Wasserstein distance test were not significantly different from those of the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test, so we have not reported them separately.

To evaluate the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test as a metric for tissue classification, each value of the table for the column "KS test" represents the percentage of Kolmogorov-Smirnov tests between the ECDF of the tissue class's population and each sample of this tissue class where the null hypothesis was correctly not rejected (the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test correctly

TABLE II
PRELIMINARY AND DISTRIBUTION ANALYSIS RESULTS

Descriptive Statistics by Tissue Class	Statistic			
	Expected Value	Standard Deviation	Deviance	KS Test
Muscle - Skeletal (1)	1.74 e8	1.19 e19	4.06	12.86%
Whole Blood (2)	1.13 e8	1.35 e19	1.00	25.54%
Brain - Spinal cord (cervical c-1) (3)	1.15 e8	8.28 e18	1.37	70.59%
Brain - Caudate (basal ganglia) (4)	1.05 e8	9.29 e18	4.23	43.22%
Brain - Nucleus accumbens (basal ganglia) (5)	1.03 e8	9.37 e18	4.23	37.72%

recognizes that the two ECDFs are from the same distribution). We can see that the highest achieved value of this statistic is found for the tissue class “Brain - Spinal cord (cervical c-1),” where 70.59% of the tissue samples whose true class was “Brain - Spinal cord (cervical c-1)” were correctly classified to be a sample of the population of this class by the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test. Because the Kolmogorov-Smirnov and Wasserstein distance tests have poor true positive classification we can determine that using distribution comparisons methods are insufficient for transcriptome-based tissue classification.

Another interesting feature of the distribution analysis results is the corroboration between the KS test figure and the preliminary analysis descriptive statistics. We can see from the preliminary analysis descriptive statistics that the standard deviation of the brain tissue classes are approximately one order of magnitude smaller than those of the “Muscle - Skeletal” and “Whole Blood” tissue classes. Likewise, the deviance of the two brain tissue classes “Brain - Caudate (basal ganglia),” “Brain - Nucleus accumbens (basal ganglia)” and “Muscle - Skeletal” are very similar (4.23, 4.23, 4.06) and higher than those for the tissue classes “Whole Blood” and “Brain - Spinal cord (cervical c-1)” (1.00, 1.37). We see that where the relative deviance is high and the standard deviation is high, we have the worst KS test value (tissue class “Muscle - Skeletal”, 12.86%) and where the relative deviance is low and the standard deviation is low we have the highest KS test value (tissue class “Brain - Spinal cord (cervical c-1)”, 70.54%). This predictable and interpretable variation of the computed KS test increases our confidence that the distribution analysis techniques were developed and implemented to the extent of their capabilities within this formulation of the tissue classification problem.

C. Results from Distribution Representation Classifier Using Support Vector Machines

The results of the support vector machine approaches were good and corroborated by the results found in [9] where the SVM approach was used to great effect on the GTEx dataset. We can see from other work toward classification of tissue samples using transcriptome data found in the GTEx dataset

Fig. 2. SVM prediction results using the distribution representations

that accurate classification results can be achieved [10] and, in comparison to [10], we achieved similar results using a smaller sample space and without using deep learning methods.

We can see the results of the SVM model using both quantification and presence data summarized by the confusion matrices in Fig 2, whose labels correspond to those in Table II. We can see from these plots that the performance of both SVM approaches is the same, with both approaches resulting in a prediction accuracy of 93.5%. Of note, the misclassifications of these two models do not follow the same pattern. Although the misclassification rate is higher in the SVM case using presence data, the misclassifications mimic underlying biological intuition. We expect tissue classes with similar biology to be “closer” to one another in the latent space of the decision than tissue classes with dissimilar biology, thereby causing the most misclassifications between tissue classes that are the most similar biologically. We see this expectation realized in the SVM experiment using presence data where 85.7% of misclassifications are between tissue types within the same region of the brain (between tissue classes “Brain - Caudate (basal ganglia)” and “Brain - Nucleus accumbens (basal ganglia)”). For the SVM experiment using quantification data many misclassifications occur between dissimilar tissue types, indicating that the latent space of the SVM decision boundary may not resemble the true decision boundary of the data i.e. this SVM model uses features of the quantification data other than those which determine biological similarity to make its decisions.

D. Distribution Representation t-SNE Visualizations

We can observe the t-SNE clusters for both the quantification and presence data in Figure 3, whose legend is Figure 4. In these plots we observe innocuous curvature in the t-SNE plot for quantification data which we can interpret as a component of “distances between clusters might not mean anything” detailed in [11]. Despite difference in cluster shapes between plots, it is evident from both that the two classes which are most similar biologically (“Brain - Caudate (basal ganglia)” and “Brain - Nucleus accumbens (basal ganglia)”) cannot be accurately split into different clusters by the t-SNE algorithm in this setting.

Another interesting feature of these results is that the tissue class with small deviance and standard deviation from our preliminary analysis (“Brain - Spinal cord (cervical c-1)”) exhibited the most compact cluster in the t-SNE visualization.

Similarly, the class with high deviance and standard deviation from our preliminary analysis (“Muscle - Skeletal”) exhibits the most spread in its cluster in the t-SNE visualization.

E. Support Vector Machines Results - Frequency Representation

Our SVM model achieved an average accuracy score of 97.02%, an average balanced accuracy score of 96.94% and an average F1 score of 96.94%. Our averaged confusion matrix showed reliable classification across all tissue types (Figure 5). The permutation importance results in Table III show the top 10 highly ranked splice junction features by their average feature importance values and their associated genes.

TABLE III
TOP TEN SPLICE JUNCTIONS WITH THE HIGHEST MEAN FEATURE IMPORTANCE VALUES ACROSS ALL ITERATIONS

Splice Junction	Gene	Mean Feature Importance
chr1.11074327.11076841	EXOSC10	.025
chr1.182385557.182385759	GLUL	.020
chr1.109237374.109237730	SARS1	.018
chr1.109415364.109421859	PSMA5	.015
chr1.202138039.202138367	ARL8A	.014
chr1.8862946.8863234	ENO1	.011
chr1.11676949.11677542	MAD2L2	.008
chr1.10179563.10179894	UBE4B	.008
chr1.153358434.153360643	S100A9	.008
chr1.109548839.109573736	GNAI3	.008

IV. CONCLUSION

In this paper we explored alternative ways of decreasing the dimensionality of our data through filtering. One method was to select only the splice junction sites which were observed enough times to exceed some threshold [12] Another was to select the top-x most relevant junction sites, as was done in other studies using genomic characteristics to classify cell type [13].

In our distribution analysis we developed a third method of filtering. In this scheme, a splice junction was considered “relevant” if the observations of this splice junction exceed a threshold-percent of all observed splice junctions using this donor. In this way we sought to remove all splice junctions that could be considered “noise” insofar as they comprised a small percentage of all junction sites with that donor. Our donor-level relevance threshold was not adequate in filtering out irrelevant splice junctions, and this method did not significantly decrease the dimensionality of our problem. Although there was some skew to the tissue empirical distributions, the small reduction in the dimensionality can be understood to be caused by the many unique splice junction sites in its tails. Because these splice junction sites had a relatively small number of total observations pertaining to a unique donor, it is easier for the unique variants that use the same donor to pass the relevance threshold. Thus, we can infer that there are many unique and infrequently occurring splice junction sites that comprise most of the empirical distribution. Extracting tissue-specific splice junctions that constitutes “noise” in the tails of this distribution could reveal additional important features.

As we observed from the results of the SVM approaches, embedding techniques that utilize only the presence of a donor location are sufficient for the accurate classification of tissues. Our t-SNE visualizations show that while there are clean clusters across histological types (i.e. brain vs. muscle vs. whole blood), there is little separability among the different subcategories of brain tissue (spinal cord vs. caudate vs. nucleus accumbens). This result may be due to our filtering method that used donor site frequency as the criteria for inclusion. By filtering our data at the donor site level, we selected the splice junctions that correspond to the primary or most expressed transcript. Primary transcripts are cell-type-specific for non-brain tissues, but the cellular specificity for brain tissues is typically driven by alternative splicing patterns [14]. This helps to explain why our t-SNE plots do not show distinction among the brain tissue types and a different filtering method may better capture the slicing variability within the brain.

In our frequency representation analysis that used the top-100 most frequently occurring splice junctions across all samples, tissue classification accuracy was high, and our average accuracy scores of 97.02% and 96.94% were similar to the accuracy rates seen in other papers, although previous studies have found that SVM is more sensitive to different normalization methods [5]. Our method of normalizing the quantification values yielded accurate predictions of tissue type, but the results may differ if we had normalized the data in a different way (e.g. standardization). Nonetheless, the findings suggest that the top-100 most frequently occurring splice junctions, along with their expression level, contain tissue-specific information about the samples. When viewing the top ten splice junctions that contributed the most to improved accuracy we see that they are all protein-coding genes that vary in their functions. Some of these findings are intuitive. For example, GLUL is a gene involved in the creation of the enzyme glutamine synthetase and is enhanced in skeletal muscles. However, the splice junction with the highest mean feature importance value was EXOSC10, a gene involved in RNA catabolic processes and is known to have low tissue specificity. This suggests that the presence of EXOSC10 is frequent but the quantification levels of EXOSC10 vary across tissue types and that the quantification value is essential for making these classifications. Further confirmation via RT-PCR will be necessary to validate these findings.

In conclusion, our research highlights the potential of using SVM models trained on RNA splice junction data in making accurate biological classifications, particularly in predicting tissue types. Further work in this domain could extend our knowledge of splice junction profiles for various tissue types. For example, future analysis could leverage this approach to facilitate the classification of healthy and diseased samples and also evaluate whether splice junction data are more informative than conventional RNA alternative transcript data that can miss subtleties in the splicing patterns. Future work should also include exploration of different feature set representations.

Fig. 3. t-SNE clustering results of distribution representation feature sets

Fig. 4. t-SNE clustering results legend

Fig. 5. Median confusion matrix across all iterations for SVM Frequency Representation Model

A. Limitations

Our analyses used only Chromosome 1 splice junction data and is currently not a genome-wide analysis of splice junction predictability. We have also chosen to predict only a subset of tissue types currently in the GTEx dataset, thereby limiting our model’s generalizability. Moreover, the dataset using the distribution representation were different from the dataset used for the frequency representation, making the results from our two approaches difficult to compare and contrast.

The common limitation of the specified approaches lies in the reduced dimensionality of the input space when compared to the source data. In the distribution analysis section, we

might have specified larger sample sizes or chosen the top-x number of most frequent splice junction sites to analyze, thereby increasing the dimensionality of the data used in our analysis. All of these changes have the potential to increase the accuracy of our distribution analysis methods, though they may simply increase the noise evident in the data. An increase of the dimensionality of the input space might have similarly helped the SVM and t-SNE approaches, with the same trade-off being increased noise in the data used.

Also, the first half of our analyses were conducted using the donor locations of observed splice junctions as a proxy for splice junction location. This removes biologically important data of the acceptor when there are repeated splice junctions with the same donor, and the unique presence of these specific donor-acceptor combinations as predictors of tissue class. Although our motivations for the decision to omit the data of acceptor location and unique splice junction pair were founded in the preliminary analysis of the paper, we recognize that in methods that specialize in high dimensional feature recognition the addition of this data will likely increase model performance.

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